

6 - Enhancing Extensive Reading in Beginner-level Indonesian Classes: Strategies, Challenges and Motivation

Sri Budi Lestari

tari0828@apu.ac.jp

Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University, Japan

Abstract

This study explores the integration of extensive reading (ER) into beginner-level foreign language classes, focusing on Indonesian learners at Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University (APU), Japan. Positive student feedback and achievement of learning targets demonstrate the feasibility of using children's books and other resources to address the shortage of graded materials for Indonesian learners. Findings suggest that ER enhances engagement, supports vocabulary acquisition, and fosters autonomous learning. This report offers a framework for implementing ER in similar contexts, particularly for languages with limited learning materials.

Keywords: Indonesian as a foreign language, beginner-level language learning, picture books, student feedback, extensive Reading,

1. Introduction

Extensive Reading (ER) is a widely recognized approach in language education, valued for providing meaningful input, fostering vocabulary acquisition, and supporting reading fluency and autonomous learning. While its application is well-established in English language teaching, its use in teaching Indonesian as a Foreign Language (BIPA) remains limited, especially for beginner learners facing a shortage of graded materials.

This report begins with a brief explanation of extensive reading, and literature review on ER implementation in beginner level of language class. Next, the description on how ER was conducted will be shown. That will include the preparation, the process on collecting the reading materials, the creation of reading records, and the setting of reading target. Finally, there will be a discussion on student feedback and some considerations that may be needed for implementing ER in Indonesian as foreign language classes, particularly for beginner-level classes.

1.1 About Extensive Reading (ER)

Extensive Reading (ER) emphasizes meaning-focused input, identified as one of the “four strands” critical for a well-balanced language course (Nation & Waring, 2020). By encouraging learners to read widely at their own pace, ER fosters natural language acquisition, fluency, and engagement. It also addresses a common imbalance in language programs, where learners often focus heavily on output-based activities while lacking sufficient opportunities for meaningful input (Renandya, 2013).

According to Day and Bamford (1998), an effective ER program should adhere to ten key principles, which are designed to ensure learners engage with reading materials that are enjoyable, accessible, and conducive to language acquisition.

1. Materials should be easy to read.
 2. A wide variety of topics should be available.
 3. Learners should have the freedom to choose what they read.
 4. Reading as much as possible should be encouraged.
-

⁶ To cite this proceeding paper: Lestari, S. B. (2024). Enhancing extensive reading in beginner-level Indonesian classes: Strategies, challenges, and learner motivation. In D. K.-G. Chan et al. (Eds.), *Evolving trends in foreign language education: Past lessons, present reflections, future directions. Proceedings from the 10th CLaSIC 2024* (pp. 65–75). Centre for Language Studies, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, National University of Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14504469>

5. The focus should be on enjoyment, information, and general understanding.
6. Reading should be its own reward.
7. The goal is to promote fast and fluent reading.
8. Individual and silent reading should be supported.
9. Teachers should provide guidance throughout the process.
10. Teachers should also serve as role models to inspire students.

These principles, as outlined by Day and Bamford, emphasize the importance of creating a learner-centred and enjoyable reading environment, which supports both linguistic and motivational development.

1.2 The Implementation of ER in Indonesian as foreign language class

Despite a growing interest in Extensive Reading (ER), as seen in its widespread adoption in English language teaching and increasing attention among educators of other Asian languages such as Japanese and Chinese, there is a scarcity of reports on its implementation in Indonesian as a Foreign Language classes. This study seeks to address this gap by exploring how ER can be incorporated into BIPA (Bahasa Indonesia untuk Penutur Asing) programs, particularly at the beginner level, and by drawing insights from relevant studies discussed in Section 2. The following research questions serve as a guide to this study:

1. How can ER be effectively integrated into beginner-level Indonesian language classes?
2. What challenges arise in implementing ER for beginner learners of Indonesian?
3. What are the benefits of ER for beginner learners, particularly in terms of vocabulary acquisition, motivation, and autonomous learning?

By bridging the gap in research on ER in BIPA programs, this study aims to provide practical strategies and insights for enhancing the teaching of Indonesian as a foreign language. It highlights the potential of ER to support meaningful input, improve learner motivation, and encourage autonomous learning, while addressing the specific needs and challenges faced by beginner-level students.

2. Literature review

Extensive Reading (ER) has gained recognition as an effective approach in foreign language education, promoting learner engagement, vocabulary acquisition, and comprehension skills. Despite its widespread application in major languages, the implementation of ER in less commonly taught languages, such as Indonesian, remains underexplored. This section reviews existing literature on ER, focusing on its application in Asian language contexts and specifically in BIPA (Bahasa Indonesia untuk Penutur Asing) programs. Subsection 2.1 examines ER implementation in other Asian languages, while subsection 2.2 addresses studies related to ER in Indonesian language teaching.

2.1 Reports of ER in Asian languages

Hitosugi and Day (2004) is one of the key studies demonstrating how ER can be incorporated into beginner-level foreign language courses, particularly for less commonly taught languages such as Asian languages. At the time, there was a scarcity of language learner literature for students learning Japanese as a foreign language. To address this, Hitosugi and Day utilized 266 children's books written for native Japanese speakers. These books were categorized into six levels of difficulty based on criteria such as the kanji characters used, the presence of furigana (pronunciation glosses), sentence length, and the amount of visual aids provided.

2.2 Study on ER in BIPA class

Isnaini et al. (2021) explored ER in the context of a BIPA class, highlighting the need for interculturally based materials and presenting a model text used in an Indonesian language institute. While the report offers recommendations and examples of learning models, including extensive reading, it does not detail the implementation or outcomes of an ER program.

At Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University (APU), Japan, the author of the current study implemented ER in BIPA classes with detailed methodologies. Lestari (2024) describes the integration of ER through in-class and outside-class activities, structured around key principles such as reading easy materials, avoiding dictionaries, and fostering autonomous learning. The activities utilized a mix of online platforms like “Room to Read” and “Let’s Read,” printed children’s books, and storybooks developed specifically for BIPA students. Challenges, such as mismatches in difficulty levels and the scarcity of Indonesian Graded Readers, were addressed by carefully curating materials and adjusting activities to learners’ proficiency levels. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of meaningful input and student engagement through activities like book talks, read-aloud sessions, and guided reading records. Feedback from students demonstrated positive outcomes, including increased vocabulary acquisition, improved comprehension, and heightened motivation. Lestari (*op. cit.*) emphasized the urgent need to develop culturally relevant graded readers to better support language acquisition and provides a framework for effectively implementing ER in BIPA programs.

3. Aims of this study

Indonesian, or Bahasa Indonesia, holds minor status in Japan and is primarily taught at the beginner level. This study aims to address the unique challenges faced by beginner learners, who often rely heavily on textbooks that may not expose them to vocabulary commonly used in real-life situations. By integrating Extensive Reading (ER) into beginner-level Indonesian language classes, the study seeks to provide learners with authentic input to enhance their motivation and foster autonomous learning.

Given the lack of graded reading materials designed specifically for second-language learners of Indonesian, this study utilizes children’s books written for native speakers as a key resource. Through its findings, the study aims to offer insights into the development and use of resources for implementing ER in BIPA classes, explore strategies for providing students with access to ER, such as through curated catalogues, present formats for recording learners’ reading progress, and analyse feedback on the effectiveness of ER activities for students with limited language proficiency.

4. Implementation method

4.1 Overview of The BIPA class in this study

The ER program or activity was conducted in Malay/Indonesian classes in Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University (APU), Japan. This course basically only teaches Indonesian but the differences and similarities between Indonesian and Malay are also given in the class as general information. Below are the list of classes and how each level correlates to BIPA level’s standard.

Table 1 - Malay/Indonesian Classes in APU

Class Name	Credit	CFER or BIPA Target
Malay/Indonesian I	4	A1 (BIPA 1)
Malay/Indonesian II	4	A2 (BIPA 2-3)
Malay/Indonesian III	4	A2 - B1 (BIPA 3-4)
Malay/Indonesian IV	2	B1 (BIPA 4-5)

Note. These are classes based on 2017 curricula. From 2023 curricula, Malay Indonesian III is divided into 2 credit classes (Malay/Indonesian III A and Malay/Indonesian III B), and Malay Indonesian IV is changed to Global Language Learning Malay/Indonesian.

The class with 4 credits has 56 meeting in one semester, Spring (April-Juli) and Fall (October-January). Thus it requires 4 meetings in one week (Monday, Tuesday, Thursday, and Friday). The curriculum is arranged that classes is not divided according to the language skills. Vocabulary and Structure, Writing, Reading, Speaking, and Listening is covered in the same subject. The students are very diverse. They have different backgrounds in terms of country of origin, native language, and cultural aspects.

4.2 Preparations

4.2.1 Collecting the books resources

Since Indonesian Graded Readers are not available, the author uses children's books. These books are written for native Indonesian speakers. Although they are created with age levels for children in mind (Levelled Readers), because the target audience is native speakers, the texts are essentially not simplified or controlled. However, children's books are also recommended and even considered to play an important role for languages that still lack Graded Readers. (Nation & Waring, 2020, p. 33; Day, R. & Bamford, 1998, p. 98).

Below are some lists of books that are used in ER activity in APU. The books that can be read online (Table 3) are those accessible through the Room to Read and Let's Read websites. These two sites have been discussed in Lestari (2024) in terms of book levels, themes, genres, and so on. The majority of printed books are books published by Litara Foundation, a partner organization of Room to Read and Let's Read as well, working to provide free books for children.

Table 2 - Printed Books list used in ER program/activity in APU

Category	Number of Titles
Bianglala Anak Nusantara Series Books (Litara Foundation)	33
Litara Foundation Big Book Series (Inovasi untuk Anak Sekolah)	17
Animal Series (Seri Hewan dan Makanannya, ect)	11
Fabel Nusantara Series	5
Translation of Children Book from other's languages	11
Graded Readers created at APU	8
Others	42
Total	94

Printed books on Table 2 include books of author's own collection and the rest are books bought by budgets from university or internal grant aid. The list of the titles from Graded Readers created in APU is shown in Lestari (2023, p. 44).

Table 3 - Online Materials used in ER program/activity in APU

Sources	Number of Titles
Room to Read (A1 level)	24
Room to Read (A2 level)	86
Let's Read (Level 0)	5
Let's Read (Level 1)	55
Let's Read (Level 2)	202

The author only recommends students to read books on those sites up to level 2 (A2). The reason is that level 3 and above use vocabulary that is beyond the scope of classroom content, and the length of text per page is generally long. Even for A1 and A2 leveled books, caution is needed when selecting and recommending them to students. For this reason, the author lists books that are considered easy and includes them in a list (Lestari, 2024, p. 102-103).

Books on Let's Read tend to have lengthy texts and challenging vocabulary. The advantage of Let's Read is that almost all of its books can be downloaded for academic purposes or to promote literacy

among younger generations. The author examines vocabulary, grammar structures, and expressions in the texts and selects several books suitable for learners at APU, both at beginner levels (levels 1 and 2) and intermediate levels (levels 3 and 4). A total of 19 books were selected (Level 0: 5 books, Level 1: 7 books, Level 2: 6 books, and Level 3: 1 book). The list of books, along with the PDF texts downloaded from Let's Read, is stored in Google Drive and the link is shared with students during the ER activity.

4.2.2 Making catalogues

In this session, three book catalogues created by the author will be presented. These catalogues are still in the draft stage or are ideas for the future

First, with the help of a research assistant, the author created data on all books (except books created in APU) in Table 2, which includes book titles, subject categories, number of sentences per page, and number of words per page for all books. A summary of this data is a catalogue listing book titles, with each book having data on its total pages, total words, and total sentences. This detailed book catalogue with word counts and difficulty levels is distributed to students in the ER Spring 2024 class.

Second, unlike the catalogue above, the author also created a reading list using a template from the online learning tool Padlet. This reading list provides online reading materials from Room to Read, Let's Read and APU books. The books are categorized by level, according to the estimated skill level of the students at APU. The advantage of Padlet is that we can easily add links and basic information is displayed; for some resources, the book cover is also displayed. This Padlet catalogue will continue to be updated. The Padlet link is shown below.

<https://padlet.com/sribudilestari/book-list-for-indonesian-beginner-level-apu-afgrdc8mzuz944b0>

Figure 1 – Screenshot of the reading list categorised by proficiency levels and created using Padlet

The third catalogue is a catalogue containing several book titles, reader reviews and borrowing links. The books in this catalogue are those that have been read by other learners in other ER-related activities. This catalogue is stored in Google Drive, and the link is shared with the students. Now there are only 5 books in the catalogue, but this will continue to be updated. The link is shown below.

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1ON74W1SqBhbVu8ikvvY-G5GgeWWNw_8YmJ7k2KNNCe7Y/edit?usp=sharing

Figure 2- Screenshot of the catalogue with reviews by other learners and location links/QR codes

Judul	Cover	Review by Students	Source	Link or QR Code
1 Belanja Bersama Ayah		<p>"The content in this book is easy to understand for a beginner like me. The story was okay, and there are also mini-games in the book for the reader as well."</p> <p>「文字が少し多くなるが新しい単語に触れられるのでとても面白い。」</p> <p>"It was hilarious to see the little cat looking for her father call out for other animals even though it is obvious that they are not her father."</p>	Room to read	Belanja Bersama Ayah
2 Kring! Kring!		<p>「思わず笑顔になってしまうのと、絵が可愛くて面白かったです。単語がわからないのは、あったけれど絵を見たら内容はわかりました。また、授業で習った大きい、小さいといった形容詞も使われて、それがわかったので良かったです!」</p> <p>"It's a really fun book to read. The vocabulary are not that difficult, almost all of them we have learnt it in the class. This book is good for starter who want to understand Indonesian language."</p> <p>"This book is good for learning adjectives"</p>	Room to read	Kring! Kring!
3 Campur, Campur, Campur		<p>"It's a fun way to learn about mixing colours in Indonesian. Buku ini buku bagus tentang warna (color)."</p> <p>「色の識別させる練習に良い本だと思った」</p> <p>"Easy to understand and the illustration was cute"</p>	Room to read	Campur, campur, campur
4 Nasi dan Goreng				
5 Nasi Putih				

4.3 Formulating the reading record

Lestari (2024) introduced several reading records used in ER activities at APU from Spring 2022 to Fall 2022. Two examples of these records are presented here, highlighting their application in Spring 2023 and Spring 2024.

In Spring 2023, the reading records were designed for intermediate-level students in Malay/Indonesian III and IV. These records emphasized content comprehension and helped students

5.1 Overview of the program

5.1.1 Spring 2023

In Spring 2023, Extensive Reading (ER) was incorporated into Malay/Indonesian III and IV as part of the students' homework. The following guidelines were provided to help students engage with ER effectively:

1. Choose books that look interesting and are easy to read.
2. Read without relying on a dictionary, if possible.
3. Feel free to read the same book multiple times.
4. Avoid looking up new vocabulary or taking notes while reading.
5. Focus on reading quickly and for enjoyment.

Students were also given specific instructions on managing their ER homework. Each Monday, 5 minutes before class ended, students selected at least one book to take home and read. At home, they completed a reading report form summarizing their reading. The following Monday, 10 minutes before class started, students gave a 1-minute presentation summarizing the book they had read. They were encouraged to retell the story without referring to their notes starting from the third week of the program.

This ER homework activity ran for a total of six weeks. The Spring 2023 class included five students from Malay/Indonesian III and two from Malay/Indonesian IV. The discussion here focuses on the experiences and outcomes of the Malay/Indonesian III students.

5.1.2 Spring 2024

The author began conducting Extensive Reading (ER) as a formal classroom activity (rather than homework) in the Spring 2024 semester. The participants included 10 students from Malay/Indonesian II and 3 students from Malay/Indonesian IV. Nevertheless, the result of Level IV activities is not going to be discussed here because their level is not beginner. The course was divided into two quarters, with ER activities implemented from the first week of the second quarter until the end of the semester (June 10 to July 19). ER sessions were held twice a week during class time, totaling 12 sessions. While this number of sessions might seem limited for an ER program, the time constraints were due to the need to cover all language skills and achieve the course's learning objectives, as detailed in Section 4.1.

The flow of ER activities during Spring 2024 was as follows:

1. **Scheduled Reading Time:** Activities were conducted 20 minutes at the start of class on Mondays and Thursdays.
2. **Book Selection Process:** Books were displayed in rows on a table. Initially, they were categorized by word count (e.g., 30–50 words, 50–100 words, etc.), but students preferred selecting books based on their covers rather than the categorized arrangement.
3. **Independent and Optional Aloud Reading:** Students read individually and silently after choosing a book. Some students opted to read aloud, which was allowed without restriction.
4. **Minimal Dictionary Use:** Dictionaries were provided on the table for reference, but students were encouraged to rely on context and visuals, using the dictionaries sparingly.
5. **Instructor Guidance:** Students were welcome to seek assistance from the instructor if they encountered challenging vocabulary.
6. **Documenting Progress:** After completing a book, students filled out a reading record form (as described in Section 4.3).

This report focuses on the results of the 10 students from Malay/Indonesian II, as their experiences form the core of the analysis.

5.2 Reading target

Day and Bamford (1998, pp. 86–87) highlight the importance of setting reading targets in Extensive Reading (ER) programs. A reading target requires students to read a specific number of

books or pages, providing a measurable way to evaluate their progress. Following this principle, a reading target of 20 books was established for the Malay/Indonesian II class's ER program in Spring 2024.

Students responded positively to the reading sessions. They were informed that completing 20 books during the second quarter would earn them full marks (100) for a designated task. To further motivate students, the author introduced an additional target mid-program. Students who read 25 or more books were eligible to earn extra credit equivalent to a quiz score. This new incentive aimed to encourage continued engagement and higher achievement. The scoring system was structured as follows:

- **20 books** : 100 points (Task score)
- **25–29 books** : 90 points (Extra Quiz score)
- **30 or more books** : 95 points (Extra Quiz score)

The overall grading system in the syllabus allocated:

- 5% to Participation,
- 25% to Tasks and Quizzes,
- 35% to the Quarter 1 Test, and
- 35% to the Quarter 2 Test and Presentation.

The scores for reading targets were calculated as part of the “Task and Quiz” category, ensuring alignment with the syllabus requirements.

5.3 The Achievement to the Reading Target

All students of Malay/Indonesian II who participated in the Spring 2024 ER program met the reading target. On average, students read 28 books during the program. Specifically:

- Two students read 32 books,
- One student read 31 books,
- Three students read 30 books,
- One student read 29 books, and
- Three students read between 20 and 23 books.

5.4 Questionnaire results

After the program concluded, the author administered a questionnaire to participating students. The questionnaire consisted of 20 questions divided into the following sections:

- Nine 5-point scale questions (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree),
- Five open-ended questions, and
- Six yes/no questions.

The questions were designed with reference to previous research by Hitosugi and Day (2004). This report focuses on the results of four 5-point scale questions (Q6–Q9) and two open-ended questions (Q10 and Q12), specifically discussing the responses of the Malay/Indonesian II program participants. Of the 10 students, 8 completed the questionnaire.

Table 4 Summary of responses for 5-point Likert scale questions (Q6–9)

Question	Response Summary	Interpretation
Q6: When I was doing ER, I looked at the pictures carefully to understand the contents.	6 students: 'Strongly Agree'; 2 students: 'Agree'	Pictures in books help beginners understand vocabulary and text. Children's books are effective starting materials for ER activities.
Q7: I like reading Indonesian books.	8 students: 'Strongly Agree' or 'Agree'	Students showed enthusiasm and positive attitudes toward reading Indonesian books, with no reluctance evident.
Q8: I want to read more Indonesian books to learn Indonesian.	3 students: 'Strongly Agree' or 'Agree'; Other responses varied	Mixed responses suggest varying levels of interest in continuing to use Indonesian books for language learning.

Q9: ER helps me to learn Indonesian (increase vocabulary, practice grammar, understand text from context and pictures).	5 students: 'Strongly Agree'; 3 students: 'Agree'	Most students recognized ER's benefits for vocabulary building, grammar practice, and comprehension.
---	---	--

In response to Q10 (Before and after your extensive reading activities, have you noticed any changes in your own learning of Indonesian or in reading itself?), students noted several positive impacts of the ER activities on their Indonesian language learning. Some observed improvements in vocabulary acquisition, as they became familiar with common words, root words, and their variations. Students appreciated the opportunity to discover word spellings and nuances, especially for words they usually only heard. The other students highlighted the benefit of learning informal and colloquial expressions that are not typically covered in class, enriching their understanding of everyday language used by locals and children.

Students also found that using picture books was particularly effective, as it allowed them to understand unfamiliar words through context and visuals rather than constant dictionary use. Additionally, a student mentioned increased ease in understanding grammatical structures, contributing to their confidence in reading Indonesian texts.

Table 5 - Summary of responses for open-ended Q10

Question	Response Summary
Q10 Before and after your extensive reading activities, have you noticed any changes in your own learning of Indonesian or in reading itself?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It was great to see the spelling and make new discoveries when looking at words in a book that I usually pronounce out loud. 2. I was able to learn not only the formal Indonesian taught in class but also the words used by locals and children. 3. I felt that my retention of words improved faster. 4. Instead of looking up every unfamiliar word, I was able to guess the meaning from the context and pictures. I also thought about whether related words had similar meanings. 5. Honestly, our vocabulary level is around that of a 3-year-old, so using local picture books is a very effective approach. Through picture books, I was also able to learn about the culture. It was also very interesting to read books made by other students. 6. I became more familiar with commonly used words and the root words and their variations. 7. I increased the number of words I can read, and understanding grammatical structures became easier.

The next bit of discussion focuses on the responses to Q12: "How many books could you read (approximately)? What made you work up to that number?" Eight students provided answers regarding the number of books they read, but only six offered reasons for achieving their respective totals. Below are their responses:

Table 6 - Summary of responses for open-ended Q12

Question	Response Summary
Q12 How many books could you read (approximately number is ok)? What made you work up to that number?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 20 books. Because I was aiming to reach the target number along with everyone in the class, not just by myself. 2. More than 30 books. I enjoy reading, so I was able to keep going while having fun. 3. 25 books. I wanted to achieve a better grade, and having classmates also motivated my competitive spirit. 4. 30 books. I chose short and easy books... and picture books were interesting. 5. 32 books. I worked hard because we would receive a grade. 6. 20 books. Because I had to read them.

The presence of classmates working toward the same goal fostered a sense of friendly competition, motivating many students to continue reading. Overall, a combination of external factors, such as grades, and intrinsic enjoyment played significant roles in sustaining their engagement with the extensive reading activity.

5.5 Suggestions for post-reading activity

Q16 asked the students “The original purpose of Extensive Reading is for enjoyment and general knowledge. What do you think is a good post-reading activity?” Below are some suggestions gathered from students.

Table 7 - Summary of responses for open-ended Q12

Question	Response Summary
Q16 The original purpose of Extensive Reading is for enjoyment and general knowledge. What do you think is a good post-reading activity?	1, I think it would be fun to have a read-aloud experience with Indonesian students (preferably children). Share what we learned from the book. 2, It would be nice to write a book review on Canva like we did this time and, if time permits, give a presentation. 3, Create our own picture book. 4. Choose one book and try translating it into Japanese or English ourselves. 5. We can engage with Indonesian culture and content.

6. Conclusion

The questionnaire results from Malay/Indonesian II ER program show that students enjoyed reading Indonesian books and found them helpful for learning. Most students liked using picture books because they made it easier to understand new words and concepts without always needing to use a dictionary.

While many students expressed a desire to read more Indonesian books to improve their language skills, the majority agreed that ER helped them learn new vocabulary and understand grammar better. The program created a fun and friendly atmosphere, where students felt motivated by their classmates and the chance to earn good grades.

Students also suggested exciting ideas for post-reading activities, like reading aloud with Indonesian children, sharing what they learned, writing book reviews, creating their own picture books, and even translating stories into Japanese or English. This shows their interest in continuing to learn and engage with the Indonesian language and culture in creative ways.

Because the small sample due to few participants in this ER program, the result must be considered as indicative, not conclusive.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported partly by JSPS KAKENHI Grant 24K04123.

References

- Day, R. R., & Bamford, J. (1998). *Extensive reading in the second language classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hitosugi, C. I., & Day, R. R. (2004). Extensive reading in Japanese. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 16.
- Isnaini, et al. (2021). Integrating cultural materials as the media for extensive reading for teaching Bahasa Indonesia as a foreign language. *Satwika: Kajian Ilmu Budaya dan Perubahan Sosial*, 5, 131–141.
- Lestari, S. B. (2023). Pengembangan bahan bacaan untuk kegiatan extensive reading di kelas Bahasa Indonesia untuk penutur asing. *Indonesian Language and Culture*, 29, 35–48. https://nihon-indonesia-gakkai.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Journal_HPISJ_No29_2023.pdf
- Lestari, S. B. (2024). Extensive reading in Indonesian for foreigners (BIPA) classes: The implementation and challenges. *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Language and Literature Preservation* (pp. 65–75). <https://penerbit.brin.go.id/others/catalog/view/1000/968/23515>
- Nation, I. S. P., & Waring, R. (2020). *Teaching extensive reading in another language*. Routledge.
- Renandya, W. A. (2013). The role of input- and output-based practice in ELT. In A. Ahmed, M. Hanzala, F. Saleem, & G. Cane (Eds.), *ELT in a changing world: Innovative approaches to new challenges* (pp. 41–52). Cambridge Scholars Publishing.